

DEVELOPMENT OF ETHANOL-BASED BIO FUEL USED FOR DOMESTIC PURPOSE

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Abstract

The report begins with an overview of the global energy landscape and the role of biofuels in mitigating carbon emissions. It then delves into the composition of sugarcane bagasse, highlighting its rich cellulose and hemicellulose content suitable for ethanol production. Methods for ethanol extraction from sugarcane bagasse are discussed, with a focus on enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation processes. Factors influencing extraction efficiency such as enzyme type, pH, temperature, and pretreatment methods are examined. By systematically conducting performance tests on a 4-stroke diesel engine with various ethanol blends, researchers and engineers can evaluate the feasibility and potential benefits of using ethanol-diesel blends as alternative fuels. E5 have less efficiency compared to other blended fuel. Generally increases with brake power. At lower power, the engine might not be operating efficiently, leading to higher fuel consumption per unit of power produced..

Keywords: Biofuel production, enzymatic hydrolysis, Flash point, Fire point, Biomass

1. Introduction

The world is mainly dependent upon non-renewable energy sources for generation of heat and power and transport. The major energy source is fossil fuel. These fuels provide about 78.4% of the final energy Consumption worldwide. Because of increasing energy requirement & impact of fossil fuel use on health & environment. According to 2023, the ethanol production Capacity in the Country is about 1380 crore liters out of which about 875 crore liters is molasses based & about 505 Crore liters is grain based. Environmental issues and shortage of fossil fuel have turned public interest to the utilization of renewable, environmentally friendly fuel such as ethanol in order to minimize the Competition between fuels and food production researchers are focusing their efforts utilization of wastes & by-products as raw materials for the production of ethanol. Bioethanol is one of the most interesting bio-fuels due to its positive impact on the environment. Currently it is mostly produced from sugar and starch containing raw material. Renewable energy capacity by 2030, India faces a tightrope walk with regard to its ethanol blending target. While ethanol blended petrol (EBP) increased from 1.6% in 2013-14 to 11.8% in 2022-23, the 20% target by 2025 has run into trouble with low sugar stocks in 2022-23 and the impending shortfall in sugarcane production this year. As evident from Minister of Consumer Affairs Piyush Goyal's statement in May, the government is looking at a major transition towards grains-based ethanol for meeting the target. The recent authorization of the National Agricultural Cooperative Marketing Federation of India (NAFED) and the National Cooperative Consumers' Federation of India (NCCF) to procure maize (corn) for supplying ethanol distilleries indicates emphasis on this transition and will boost an organized maize-feed supply chain for ethanol. In Ecuador, ethanol production generates socio-economic opportunities in several provinces.. analyzed the relationship between economic growth and the agricultural production structure. This study indicates that, although the provinces of Pichincha and Guayas have a high Gross Value Added in the agricultural sector, they do not exceed the median of, with strategic development being significant. During the last decades, the Ecuadorian government implemented policies to promote the development of renewable energies, which did not have the expected results. The Republic's Constitution of 1998 established initiatives in using renewable energy. However, the 2008 Constitution strengthened this principle by integrating the concept of energy efficiency, by, for instance, incorporating vehicles benefiting from an electricity system and preferential energy tariffs.

2. Method & Material

Ethanol extraction from sugarcane molasses involves a multi-step process that harnesses the sugars present in molasses to produce ethanol, a renewable biofuel.

A. SUGARCANE BAGASSE

Figure 1: Sugarcane bagasse

Bagasse is the dry pulpy fibrous material that remains after crushing sugarcane or sorghum stalks to extract their juice. It is used as a biofuel for the production of heat, energy, and electricity, and in the manufacture of pulp and building materials.

B. YEST

Figure 2: Yest

Yeast is a single-cell organism, called *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, which needs food, warmth, and moisture to thrive. It converts its food—sugar and starch—through fermentation, into carbon dioxide and alcohol. Yeasts can directly ferment simple sugars into ethanol while other type of feedstocks must be converted to fermentable sugars before it can be fermented to ethanol.

C. FERMENTATION JAR WITH AIR LOCK

Figure 3: Fermentation jar with air lock, Silicon CorkLarge vessels or tanks where fermentation occurs under controlled conditions.

D. DISTILLATION EQUIPMENT

Figure 4: Boilers, glass jar, water container for cooling

Including stills, boilers, condensers, and columns used to separate ethanol from water and impurities.

i. Definition

Bioethanol, also known simply as ethanol, is a renewable, bio-based fuel produced through the fermentation of biomass rich in carbohydrates, such as sugarcane, corn, wheat, or cellulose-rich materials. It is a type of alcohol that can be used as a fuel additive, blended with gasoline to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil fuels. Bioethanol is commonly used as a transportation fuel in vehicles equipped with flexible fuel engines, where it can be blended with gasoline in varying proportions. Additionally, bioethanol has applications in industrial processes, chemical synthesis, and as a solvent in various industries. As a renewable energy source, bioethanol contributes to reducing carbon dioxide emissions and mitigating climate change while promoting energy security and rural development.

ii. How Bioethanol works.

The process of how bioethanol works involves several stages, from its production to its utilization as a fuel:

1. **Production:** Bioethanol is typically produced through the fermentation of biomass, which is rich in carbohydrates. Biomass sources include sugarcane, corn, wheat, or cellulose-rich materials like agricultural residues, energy crops, or even municipal solid waste. The biomass undergoes various pretreatment and conversion processes to release fermentable sugars, which are then fermented by microorganisms such as yeast to produce ethanol and carbon dioxide.
2. **Fermentation:** During fermentation, yeast or other microorganisms metabolize the sugars present in the biomass feedstock, converting them into ethanol and carbon dioxide through anaerobic metabolism. The fermentation process is carefully controlled in terms of temperature, pH, and nutrient levels to optimize ethanol production.
3. **Distillation:** After fermentation, the resulting mixture, known as "beer" or "mash," undergoes distillation to separate ethanol from water and other impurities. Distillation involves heating the mixture to vaporize the ethanol, which has a lower boiling point than water, and then condensing the vapor back into liquid form. This process concentrates the ethanol, producing a solution with higher ethanol content.
4. **Dehydration:** The ethanol obtained from distillation typically contains some water, which needs to be removed to increase its purity and concentration. Dehydration processes such as molecular sieves, membrane separation, or azeotropic distillation are employed to remove water from ethanol, yielding anhydrous ethanol with high purity.
5. **Utilization as a Fuel:** Bioethanol can be used as a renewable fuel in various applications. In transportation, it is commonly blended with gasoline to produce ethanol-gasoline blends such as E10 (10% ethanol, 90% gasoline), E85 (85% ethanol, 15% gasoline), or even higher blends. Ethanol-gasoline blends can be used in conventional gasoline engines with minimal modifications, and vehicles equipped with flexible fuel engines can run on high ethanol blends like E85. When used as a fuel, bioethanol undergoes combustion in engines, producing energy in the form of heat that is converted into mechanical work to propel vehicles.

Overall, bioethanol offers a renewable and sustainable alternative to fossil fuels, contributing to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, promoting energy security, and fostering rural development. Its production and utilization form a crucial part of the global effort to transition towards cleaner and more sustainable energy sources.

Methods

Figure 7. A four-step process for ethanol production from biomass

Pretreatments

The main objective of the pretreatments is to break down the lignin structure and disrupt the crystalline structure of cellulose for enhancing enzymes accessibility to the cellulose during the hydrolysis step. These pretreatments may be biological, chemical, and physical processes that are used individually, combined, and/or sequentially. The natural structure of lignocellulosic material is extremely recalcitrant to enzymatic hydrolysis. Therefore, the pretreatment step is required for efficient enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose by removal of lignin and hemicellulose, reduction of cellulose crystallinity and increase the porosity of the biomass. Each pretreatment has a different effect on the cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin fraction.

It is necessary to choose suitable pretreatment methods for SCB since different lignocellulosic materials have different physico-chemical characteristics. An efficient pretreatment should (1) improve the formation of fermentable sugars, (2) avoid the loss or degradation of carbohydrates, (3) avoid the formation of inhibitory by-products, and (4) be cost-effective, an ideal pretreatment should be economically efficient, low energy consumption, and producing less or no residues. High digestibility of cellulose and versatility of feedstock are also important in the pretreatment process. In addition, other factors such as low sugar decomposition, low water or high solids, and low chemical consumption during the process should be considered. Besides that, the pretreatment should be performed at low operational risk and safe.

Steam explosion pretreatment

Steam explosion is one of the most efficient methods to deconstruct the plant cell wall macromolecular organization. This process occurs both chemically and physically by revealing the lignocellulosic materials to high temperatures ranging from 160 to 260°C for reaction times varying from 2 to 30 min in the saturated steam either in the absence or presence of an exogenous acid or basic catalyst. The steam is able to expand the cell wall of the polysaccharide fiber and destroys cell structure into small pieces and breaks down the lignin network. This process would increase the accessibility of the enzyme to cellulose by exposing internal cellulose surface, which acetyl groups of hemicellulose can be hydrolyzed to acetic acid. The physical forces cause partial hemicellulose solubilization and lignin reorganization. The major variables that affect steam explosion pretreatment efficacy include biomass origin, particle size, temperature, residence time, and moisture content.

When pretreatment is performed in the presence of an acid catalyst such as sulfuric (H₂SO₄) or phosphoric (H₃PO₄) acids, the need for time and temperature decreases substantially depending on the strength of the acid and its actual concentration in relation to the dry mass of the biomass. In addition, this process can remove hemicelluloses almost completely, whereas lignin is modified to a deeper extend, thus making the cellulosic materials more susceptible to enzymatic or acid hydrolysis. There are several advantages of steam explosion pretreatment which includes lower environmental impact, cost-effectiveness, greater energy efficiency, and less or no chemical usage. Also, to obtain the same particle size of the substrate, steam explosion method requires

a 70% lower energy consumption compared to the conventional mechanical process. The main drawbacks of steam explosion pretreatment are the partial degradation of hemicelluloses and the formation of toxic components that could affect the enzymatic hydrolysis and fermentation process.

Liquid hot water

Liquid hot water (LHW) pretreatment is performed at various temperatures from 160 to 240°C in the liquid state with water instead of steam. The LHW process primarily maximizes the solubilization of hemicellulose, partial removal of lignin, and making cellulose more accessible to the enzyme. In addition, the formation of the undesirable side products in liquid fraction can be reduced due to solubilized hemicellulose mostly appears in oligomers forms. The LHW pretreatment cleaves hemicellulose linkages and liberates various acids during the process. These acids help to hydrolyze hemicellulose to monomeric sugars, which can be subsequently degraded to aldehydes (i.e., furfural from five carbon sugars and HMF from six carbon sugars). LHW has a great potential to be chosen as a pretreatment step in the biorefinery process as it can be considered as a green technology.

During high temperature pretreatment processes, water molecules penetrate the biomass cell wall and hydrate cellulose, with the partial removal of hemicellulose and minor amount of lignin. The advantage of using the neutral method compared to the dilute-acid and alkaline catalyzed pretreatments is to avoid the chemical use in excess, because pH close to neutral does not cause corrosion from occurring, and the formation of excess furans during sugar degradation reactions can be eluded. However, sugar release yields from LHW pretreated biomass are lower than diluted acid pretreated biomass, otherwise higher pretreatment temperature and longer residence time are required for comparable performance. The LHW has a few advantages compared to other pretreatment methods such as no additional catalysts or chemicals, operates at relatively moderate temperature, high hemicelluloses recovery, low levels of inhibitory by-products and cost-effective.

Preparations

Preparation Of Sugarcane Bagasse

The sugarcane bagasse was obtained from area around, the sugarcane bagasse was thoroughly washed with tap water and cut into smaller pieces. Then sugarcane bagasse was dried in oven at 60°C for 3 days. It was treated at 60°C because if the temperature was higher, it will affect the enzymes in the sugarcane bagasse. Once dried, the sugarcane bagasse was grinded using the grinding machine. The sugarcane bagasse sample was sealed in the seal bag or poly bag and stored in room conditions.

Buffer preparation

Buffer was used to dilute the enzyme alpha-amylase and glucoamylase. Enzyme reaction will be more effective if dilute with buffer compared to distilled water. There were two types of buffers prepared which were phosphate buffer for α -enzymes and acetic acid with sodium acetate buffer for glucoamylase. The prepared buffer was covered with aluminum foil and kept at room temperature for further use.

Liquefaction of sugarcane

10g of sugarcane was weighed. The weighed sample was placed into conical flask and 200ml of distilled water was added to the sample. 0.5 ml of NaOH was prepared to be added at this step to adjust the pH of the slurry to 4.5. Next 0.2 microliters of enzyme alpha- amylase was added to the mixture. The alpha-amylase was diluted with phosphate buffer before added to the slurry. The mixture was heated until 50°C. Alpha- amylases will breakdown the cellulose into smaller size called dextrin.

Saccharification of sugarcane bagasse

The mixture was cooled down to 40°C. Then, 0.2 microliters of secondary enzyme, glucoamylase was added to the mixture. Glucoamylase was diluted with acetic acid with sodium acetate buffer before added to the slurry. The mixture was maintained at 50°C as the glucoamylase hydrolyzed the dextrin to fermentable glucose. The mixture was cooled down to 32°C and 10 ml of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (baker yeast) was added to the sample before transferred to conical flask.

Fermentation of sugarcane

In fermentation process, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (baker yeast) was used to ferment the simple sugar to ethanol and carbon dioxide. To determine the effects of pH on ethanol yield, the temperature was kept constant at 37°C while the pH was varied from 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5 and 5. To determine the effect of temperature on ethanol yield, the pH was kept constant at 4.5. The fermentation process continued for 48 hours.

Distillation of ethanol

After 48 hours, the sample was filtered using Whatman Filter Paper to separate the ethanol from the residue. The bioethanol was distilled using rotary evaporator. The sample was heated at 80°C to get the bioethanol.

Determine bioethanol yield

Bioethanol produced was analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). 20 μ L of the sample was injected into HPLC system to determine the bioethanol yield. Fatty acid composition in virgin coconut oil was analyzed using HPLC method. The HPLC analysis parameters were determined using the following conditions: column, C18 RP (53 x 7mm); injector temperature was 30°C, 20 μ L of the sample was injected into the HPLC system. The mobile phase was phosphoric acid and the flow rate was 1.5mL/min; and detection was set at a wavelength of 210 nm.

RESULT

Figure 8: Ethanol performance test curve

Procedure:

Ensuring that the diesel engine is in good condition and properly calibrated. Setting up the necessary instrumentation to measure performance parameters such as Brake power, Fuel consumption, Brake thermal efficiency and engine temperature. Prepare the ethanol blends (E5, E7.5, E10) by mixing the appropriate proportions of ethanol with diesel fuel of E5(Ethanol 25ml Diesel 475ml), E7.5(Ethanol 35ml Diesel 465ml), E10(Ethanol 50ml Diesel 450ml). and Conducted baseline performance tests using pure diesel fuel to establish reference values for comparison. Gradually introduce each ethanol blend and conduct performance tests under similar operating conditions as the baseline tests. Measure and record performance parameters for each blend. Analysing the test data to compare the performance of the engine with different ethanol blends. Evaluate parameters such as fuel consumption, and engine efficiency. Based on the performance evaluation, optimize the ethanol blending ratio to achieve desired performance targets and maintaining engine reliability

Conclusion

The extraction of ethanol from sugarcane bagasse offers a promising opportunity for sustainable fuel production. The performance test carried out on a diesel engine, using different ethanol blends, confirms the effectiveness of ethanol as a fuel additive. Among the tested blends, the E10 blend proves to be the best choice, exhibiting superior engine performance and reducing emissions effectively. This discovery not only emphasizes the potential of ethanol as a renewable energy source but also highlights its role in mitigating the environmental impacts associated with conventional fossil fuels. As we continue to explore alternative energy solutions, harnessing ethanol from sugarcane bagasse represents a significant stride towards a greener and more sustainable future.

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